

Djinguereber Mosque

also known as “Mosquée de Djinguereber”, “Jinggar-Ey Beer”

By Akshay Sarathi, Texas A&M University

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The Djinguereber Mosque, also known as the Mosquée de Djinguereber in French, is a large mud-brick mosque and Islamic learning center located in city of Timbuktu, Mali. Records state that it was constructed in 1327CE under the patronage of the emperor of Mali, Musa I (aka Mansa Musa) (r.c.1312-1337), who is said to have given the architect, Abu Ishaq Al Sahili 200kg (or 40,000 mithqals) of gold as payment for the project. However, this remains an apocryphal tale and there currently exists no way to verify it. The entire structure is constructed of mud brick like many other West African mosques (especially the Great Mosque of Djenne). However, in the 1960s a portion of the northern façade of the Djinguereber Mosque was reinforced using alhore stone (a local limestone used extensively in construction in and around Timbuktu). The minaret is also constructed of limestone but covered in mud. The mud bricks of which the Djinguereber Mosque is constructed are composed of mud, straw, sand, and water. Timber supports are also used throughout the structure. The Djinguereber Mosque houses one of the madrassas associated with the University of Timbuktu, a learning institution of great pedigree and antiquity in the region. Three mosques/madrassas associated with the University of Timbuktu are the Sankore Mosque (constructed in 989CE), the Djinguereber Mosque (constructed 1327CE), and the Sidi Yahya Mosque (constructed c.1400CE). The University and its associated madrassas were badly affected by the Saadian invasion and conquest of the Songhai Empire in the 1590s CE. Scholars from Timbuktu were forcibly marched across the desert to Morocco. Only one returned to Timbuktu, decades later. The mosques/madrassas of Timbuktu house an impressive collection of medieval Arab texts, a testament to the reputation of medieval Timbuktu as a great medieval center of learning. More recent tragedies have been associated with the Djinguereber Mosque was a stampede in 2010 during the festival of Mawlid (the birthday of the Prophet Muhammad), in which around 30 people were killed and countless other injured. In 2012, militants associated with the group Ansar Dine (“Defenders of Faith”) took over the city and began systematically destroying the mud-brick tombs associated with the mosques of the city. They destroyed 16 tomb-shrines associated with ancient holy men. The Djinguereber Mosque itself, however, was relatively undamaged. Other factors affecting the Djinguereber Mosque's preservation are the increased desertification and consequent uptick in sand activity in the region. The trees that provided timber for the mosques have also vanished from the region due to climate change. However, a corps of specialist mud-brick craftsmen exists to maintain the mosques of Timbuktu, even though the task seems increasingly difficult with each passing year. Some funds have been allotted for the preservation of the Djinguereber Mosque due to its status as a UNESCO World Heritage site. The Aga Khan Trust for Culture, for instance, funded a 4-year project to repair and rehabilitate the mosque in 2006. The Djinguereber Mosque remains an important cultural and religious icon to the people of region and of significant cultural importance to the world

Date Range: 1327 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Timbuktu

Region tags: Africa

The modern city of Timbuktu, Mali.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Slade, T. (2018). The Destruction of Memory. *Journal of Architectural Education*, 72(2), 208-211.
- Source 2: Adahl, K. (1993). The Islamic architecture and art in sub-Saharan Africa: A problem of identity. *Culture in Africa: An Appeal for Pluralism*, 29, 131.
- Source 3: Morris, James, and Suzanne Preston Blier. *Butabu: adobe architecture of West Africa*. Princeton Architectural Press, 2004.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://zamaniproject.org/site-mali-timbuktu-djingareyber-mosque.html#header5-a9>
- Source 1 Description: The Zamani Project's documentation of the Djinguereber Mosque.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: "Excavation" in the sense of the deliberated dismantling and digging up of the tomb-shrines associated with the Djinguereber Mosque in 2012 by Ansar Dine.

↳ Type of excavation:

– Illicit

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2012

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ansar Dine

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is associated with a fresh-water well.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Notes: A well has been built at the Djinguereber Mosque

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

Notes: A well has been constructed at the Djinguereber Mosque

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque lies in the heart of the city of Timbuktu

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: However, the relatively small size of Timbuktu makes the Djinguereber Mosque easily accessible to rural communities in the region

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: A mosque, its minarets, and associated tomb-shrines are present

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: A freshwater well

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was added to over the years, with extensions, tombs, and minarets added over time. They are not part of a single construction phase.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: Desert + well

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The surrounding desert and the well are significant features associated with the Djinguereber Mosque

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque serves as a large place of worship

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Muslim worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Like other mosques, the Djinguereber Mosque is a communal place of worship, but individual worship takes place as well.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was constructed in 1327CE has been mostly maintained and has remained in use since then.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is was regularly expanded by later rulers of the region and by the local community. A dedicated corps of mud-brick architects is tasked with the maintenance of the mosque.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: The tomb-shrines were deliberately destroyed by the Ansar Dine group in 2012. The mosque itself was relatively unharmed.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For religious reasons

–As the result of war

Notes: Many of the tomb-shrines associated with the mosque were deliberately destroyed in 2012 by the Ansar Dine group

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: The destruction of the tomb-shrines of the mosque was not due to a natural phenomenon.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: The mosque was expanded and maintained over time.

↳ In modernity

- Renaissance
- Post-Renaissance

Notes: Mud-brick architecture requires maintenance. This means that the mosque has to have been maintained over time in order to remaining standing. However, major renovations took place in the 20th century, when alhore stone was used to reinforce the northern façade. The surviving minaret also has an alhore core faced with mud.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

- Yes [specify]: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to the worship of Allah

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

- Yes [specify]: There are tomb-shrines of Muslim "saints" associated with the Djinguereber Mosque. In 2012, many of these were destroyed by the Ansar Dine group, who identified them with idolatry.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

- Yes

Notes: There are tomb-shrines associated with spiritual leaders of the past. Many of these were destroyed in 2012 by the Ansar Dine group, who accused the locals of idolatry.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

- I don't know

Notes: I am not sure about the state of affairs at the Djinguereber Mosque, but in many other mosques families of spiritual leaders form a tomb-shrine cluster.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

- Yes

↳ Body present:

– Yes

Notes: The bodies of past religious leaders are present

↳ Part of body present:

– No

Notes: Presumably, the entire body of past spiritual leaders are present.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– I don't know

Notes: The tombs and tomb-shrines associated with the Djinguereber Mosque could be associated with a particular family or group. They certainly mostly belong to past spiritual leaders.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque was commissioned by Mansa Musa (r.c.1312-1337CE) from the architect Abu Ishaw Al Sahili

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Notes: Specialist mud-brick architects likely built the Djinguereber Mosque

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The mud-brick architecture of West Africa is built and maintained by specialist craftsmen who pass their skills down the generations. Whether slaves/corvee laborers/indentured servants/captured enemies built the Djinguereber Mosque remains unknown.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The reason for the construction of the Djinguereber Mosque remain unknown. Local tradition ascribes its construction to the famous emperor of Mali, Mansa Musa.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– I don't know

Notes: There are tomb-shrines associated with the Djinguereber Mosque, but I do not know if one of the holy people to whom the tomb-shrines belong is associated with the construction of the Mosque.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The reason for the construction of the Djinguereber Mosque remain unknown

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: Local tradition ascribes its construction to the famous emperor of Mali, Mansa Musa, who financed its construction

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque was likely constructed as an act of piety by the emperor of Mali, Mansa Musa.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: That said, sacred scriptures are housed in mosques across the world. Also note that the Djinguereber Mosque is also a madrassa, which means that significant texts were and still are stored there. In fact, Timbuktu is well known for its collection of medieval manuscripts.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The minarets are attached to the main structure of the Djinguereber Mosque, while there are tomb-shrines surrounding the mosque.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque itself is the most important structure, with the tomb-shrines assuming lesser importance.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque itself is a monumental structure, capable of holding 2000 worshippers at a time.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is itself a monumental structure, large enough to hold roughly 2000 worshippers.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: The Zamani Project may have more data about this. However, data available to me suggests that the Djinguereber Mosque is a fairly large structure, capable of holding at least 2000 worshippers. It has three inner courtyards, two minarets, and twenty-five rows of pillars.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The tallest feature associated with the Djinguereber Mosque would be its main minaret.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The Zamani Project may have more data about this. However, data available to me suggests that the Djinguereber Mosque is a fairly large structure, capable of holding at least 2000 worshippers. It has three inner courtyards, two minarets, and twenty-five rows of pillars.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The Zamani Project may have more data about this. However, data available to me suggests that the main minaret of the Djinguereber Mosque is its tallest feature

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

Notes: Sand is mixed in precise quantities with earth and clay to create a building material of exact composition by the specialist architects of Timbuktu.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Mud plaster it used to face the mosque

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Timber used to be available locally, but climate change has caused large trees to vanish from the region. Timber for the maintenance of the mosque has to be imported now.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: Timber used to be available locally, but climate change has caused large trees to vanish from the region. Timber for the maintenance of the mosque has to be imported now.

↳ Grass

– Yes

Notes: Grass or straw is mixed with clay, earth, and sand to produce the mud bricks used for the construction and maintenance of the mosque.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: While most of the structure is composed of mud brick, the minaret has a core of alhore limestone, and the northern façade of the Djinguereber Mosque has been reinforced with the same stone.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: Fibers are also used to hold the mud together

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: A specific building material composed of precise quantities of sand, earth, clay, and straw are used in the construction and maintenance of the Djinguereber Mosque.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: While the Djinguereber Mosque is itself a beautiful structure, to my knowledge no elements specifically meant to be decorative have been included in its construction.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque, while beautiful, does not have any iconography associated with it, including Arabic calligraphy that at times has been used to adorn mosques around the world.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: There are tomb-shrines of past Muslim spiritual leaders associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: Perhaps "veneration" of past Muslim spiritual leaders in the area would be a better way to phrase how the locals with the dead buried in the tomb-shrines associated with the Djinguereber Mosque

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: There are tomb-shrine associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

– Other [specify]: Bodies may be made ready with the aid of the authorities of the Djinguereber Mosque.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: But offerings are left at the tomb-shrines associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: There are tomb-shrines of past Muslim spiritual leaders associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are tomb-shrines of past Muslim spiritual leaders associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

Notes: There are tomb-shrines of past Muslim spiritual leaders associated with the Djinguereber Mosque. These may be associated with specific families.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There are tomb-shrines of past Muslim spiritual leaders associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah. Whether Allah is considered to reside in the mosque is dependent on local Islamic beliefs.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque is dedicated to Allah, considered to be unquestionably good and merciful.

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: None

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether the divine communicates with the living at the Djinguereber Mosque (especially through the tomb-shrines) is dependent on local religious belief.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: There are tomb-shrines associated with past spiritual leaders at the Djinguereber Mosque

Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: There are tomb-shrines associated with past spiritual leaders at the Djinguereber Mosque. Whether they can be seen is dependent on local religious belief.

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: There are tomb-shrines associated with past spiritual leaders at the Djinguereber Mosque. Whether they can be felt is dependent on local religious belief.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: There are tomb-shrines associated with past spiritual leaders at the Djinguereber Mosque. Whether these past spiritual leaders communicate directly with the living is dependent on local religious belief.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether nonhuman supernatural beings are present is dependent on local religious belief. It is entirely possible that Islam syncretized with traditional African religions, meaning that other than human spirits could be associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether nonhuman supernatural beings are present and communicate with the living at this place is dependent on local religious belief. It is entirely possible that Islam syncretized with traditional African religions, meaning that other than human spirits could be associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: I don't know if the spiritual leaders whose tomb-shrines are associated with the Djinguereber Mosque count as mixed human-divine beings. It is possible that they do, but this is dependent on local perceptions of those buried in the tomb-shrines.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: I don't know if the spiritual leaders whose tomb-shrines are associated with the Djinguereber Mosque communicate with the living. It is possible that they do, but this is dependent on local perceptions of those buried in the tomb-shrines.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Allah is not represented in the form of a cult statue at the Djinguereber Mosque

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether supernatural monitoring takes place at the Djinguereber Mosque, especially through its tomb-shrines, is dependent on local religious belief.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether the humans who worship at the Djinguereber Mosque communicate with Allah and, even more likely, the spiritual leaders buried in the tomb-shrine associated with the mosque, is dependent on local religious belief.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Large scale Muslim prayer services are held at the Djinguereber Mosque. However, individual prayer may also take place.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: The Djinguereber Mosque can hold 2000 people. Many more can gather outside

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Everyday and on specific festival days associated with the Muslim calendar. Rituals rooted more locally may also take place at the Djinguereber Mosque.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Islam in Africa, orthodoxy is hard to maintain other than adherence to broad practices. More local practice rooted in non-Islamic or pre-Islamic traditions may not been seen by worshippers as incompatible with Islam, even if religious authorities may think so.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Islam in Africa, orthopraxy is hard to maintain other than adherence to broad practices. More local practice rooted in non-Islamic or pre-Islamic traditions may not been seen by worshippers as incompatible with Islam, even if religious authorities may think so.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Islam in Africa, intoxicants and mind-altering substances could definitely be used in religious practice, especially in association with the tomb-shrines located at the mosque.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether sacrifices/offerings are made especially at the tomb-shrines associated with the Djinguereber Mosque remains unknown.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Material offerings could be present at the tomb-shrine associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: Muslims are enjoined to worship five times a day

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: The mud-brick structure of the Djinguereber Mosque must be maintained regularly or it will collapse.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

Notes: While there are specific rituals associated with the maintenance of the mud brick structure, I do not know if cleansing the Djinguereber Mosque takes place as part of its renewal/repair.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The mud-brick structure of the Djinguereber Mosque must be maintained regularly or it will collapse.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: There is a corps of specialist mud-brick architects present at Timbuktu dedicated to the maintenance of the mosque and other mud-brick structures of the city.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

– obligatory for all

– I don't know

Notes: Pilgrimage is generally encouraged in Islam. I do not know if there are specific pilgrimages associated with the Djinguereber Mosque

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Notes: The Djinguereber Mosque was constructed as an act of piety by the emperor of Mali, Mansa Musa (r.c.1312-1337CE)

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

Notes: Pilgrimages to the Djinguereber Mosque and its associated tomb-shrines could be associated with significant life events.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– I don't know

Notes: Given the role that Timbuktu has played on trade routes in the region, there are likely established trade/pilgrimage routes associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: But feasting does occur as part of the annual renewal or repair of the Djinguereber Mosque

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: There are specific Islamic festivals such as the Eids, the start of Ramadan, and Mawlid, associated with the Djinguereber Mosque. There could also be more local festivals that take place at the Djinguereber Mosque

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The renewal/repair of the Djinguereber Mosque every year is a celebratory event.

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: There are no cult statues

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: The Djinguereber Mosque can hold 2000 within it, but many more could gather outside.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: Feasting takes place as part of annual renewal/repair of the Djinguereber Mosque

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Islam in Africa, divination could very plausibly be practiced at the mosque, especially through bibliomancy.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Islam in Africa and the fact that the Djinguereber Mosque is associated with an ancient madrassa, spiritual and physical healing practices could definitely take place at the mosque.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Imams and other Muslim religious leaders are associated with the Mosque. Whether there exists a separate/parallel religious structure associated with the tomb-shrines remains unknown.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they have to be male, according to Islamic orthodoxy. However, given the syncretic nature of African Islam, it is entirely possible that female religious leaders exist and are associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the large size of the Djinguereber Mosque, this seems highly likely.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, an ancient madrasa is associated with the Mosque.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: A specialist corps of mud-brick architects is dedicated to the maintenance of the Djinguereber Mosque.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Notes: This seems highly likely, given that the Djinguereber Mosque is an ancient institution and has an associated madrasa.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Notes: I do not know how the Djinguereber Mosque supports itself economically.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– I don't know

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– I don't know

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– I don't know

↳ Function for water management:

– I don't know

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Education - there is a madrassa associated with the Djinguereber Mosque.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The madrassa of the Djinguereber Mosque is ancient and has served as a center for Islamic and non-Islamic learning for centuries.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Other than the Quran, I don't believe so.